

THE ROLE OF ERRORS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

Isomiddinova Dilnoza Ulugbek kizi

Fergana region Uchkuprik district

Teacher of English school № 27

Annotation: By this article you can get information about the role of errors in English language teaching.

Key words: ungrammatical, semantically, linguistic, incompetency, acquisition, self-correct, language transfer, overgeneralization, simplification, underuse, fossilization, lack of the knowledge of the rules, interference.

Errors are not always bad, rather they are crucial parts and aspects in the process of learning a language. They may provide insights into the complicated processes of language development as well as a systematic way for identifying, describing and explaining students' errors.

Error analysis is a very important area of applied linguistics and of the second and foreign language learning. Applied linguistics, as a field, tries to deal with the problems and issues related to language, as well as to its learning and teaching; it also attempts to give solutions for these problems and issues. Error analysis provides a deep insight for understanding of the process of language learning.

Errors are the result of incomplete learning and linguistic incompetency of the learners and errors cannot be self-corrected.

Mistakes are the results of poor performance of language due to many factors like fatigue and carelessness on the part of learners etc. Learners have the knowledge of the correct linguistic form and they can self-correct themselves on the basis of their linguistic knowledge. This is the basic difference between errors and mistakes. And, for the correct analysis, one should be very much clear about the identification of errors. They produce ungrammatical and semantically incorrect sentences at the very earlier stage of their acquisition and later on, by getting the instructions and feedback

from their adults they correct themselves. L2 learners also go through the same process while learning any languages. That's why there is no much difference between the processes of learning the second or the foreign language and the first language acquisition.

Additionally, there are different reasons behind errors committed by the learners. One reason can be the insufficient material for language teaching or the lack of teachers' adequacy in language teaching. Some other causes of error analysis given by the researchers are listed below

- a. Language transfer
- b. Overgeneralization
- c. Simplification
- d. Underuse
- e. Fossilization
- f. Lack of the knowledge of the rules
- g. Interference

Now, we would elaborate some of them one by one to see how these factors are bringing about errors in the language learning.

Language transfer refers to the position in which one language is learned in the presence of other language. Sometimes on the basis of similarities in two languages, this has a positive effect on language learning and in the form of language differences, it interferes the second and foreign language learning.

Overgeneralization refers to the situation in which one form or rule of the language is overgeneralized over the other forms. The extending use of certain forms refers to the overgeneralization and becomes the cause of errors in language learning. This phenomenon is also observed in children while learning their first language.

Simplification refers to the situation when learners avoids the use of the complex structure and prefers to use the very simple forms. Sometimes, this also results in the form of errors.

Fossilization refers to the situation when linguistic or grammatical development in certain areas is stopped while as, in other linguistic areas, the learner is developing his/her knowledge.

This can also be the cause of learner's errors. Lack of the knowledge of the rules is also one of the major reasons of learners' errors. Sometimes, learners do not have sufficient knowledge about the rules of the language, and this phenomenon results into the errors and mistakes in language and hinders the language learning.

Language learning does not have to be based on speaking, mistakes, and repeated correction. Indeed, if your goal is good English — that is, if you want to be able to speak and write in English with few mistakes and understand English-language television — the feedback-based method is the wrong way to do it. It builds your knowledge very slowly and depends on a good instructor. As a result, only intensive, long-term courses with competent teachers can give satisfactory results, but these are very expensive and very impractical.

References:

1. Corder, S. P. (1967). The significance of learners' errors. *Int. Rev. Appl. Linguist.*
1. Corder, S. P. (1971). *Idiosyncratic Dialects and Error Analysis* (p. 14). Groos, Heidelberg.